

Fries Reaction. Part-XII: Preparation of Hydroxydiarylsulphones

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A few Hydroxyarylsulphones have been prepared by the Fries migration of the aryl-*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonates of phenol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol, *o*-chlorophenol, *o*-nitrophenol, α -naphthol in absence of solvent at elevated temperatures (130°-140°). The type of isomer (ortho or para) has been supported by ultra-violet spectra study.

THE hydroxysulphones are well known as anti-septics. Recently Agripat¹ has reported that they are useful as fungicides and bactericides. In continuation of our work on hydroxydiarylsulphones²⁻⁵, we have carried out Fries reaction of *p*-chlorobenzenesulphonates of phenol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol, *o*-chlorophenol, *o*-nitrophenol, α -naphthol, etc. The Fries reaction of phenyl-*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonates gave mixtures of two isomers (ortho and para). Both isomers were separated and their constitutions identified by u.v. spectra. *p*-Chlorobenzenesulphonates of *m*-cresol, *o*-nitrophenol and α -naphthol gave *p*-isomer while that of *o*-cresol and *p*-chlorophenol gave *o*-isomer which is also supported by u.v. spectra. The hydroxysulphones were methylated.

Ultraviolet spectra study

Intramolecular hydrogen bonding in phenol has been detected by ultraviolet absorption spectra⁶⁻⁸. Absorption of light in ortho hydroxysulphones in non-polar solvent like cyclohexane is at higher wavelength than in polar solvent like ethanol. On the one hand, in *p*-hydroxysulphones, absorption of light in cyclohexane is at shorter wavelength than in alcohol. The u.v. spectra study of diarylsulphones (recorded in Table 3) reveals the conclusion that formation of *p*-isomer predominate in the rearranged product from phenyl, *m*-cresyl, *o*-nitrophenyl and α -naphthyl-*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonates. Similarly formation of ortho isomer predominates in hydroxysulphones obtained from *o*-cresyl and *o*-chlorophenyl-*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonates (see graphs A to F).

Experimental

a) Preparation of *p*-chlorobenzenesulphonates

Phenol (0.05 mole) and *p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl-chloride (0.05 mole) were condensed using acetone as solvent. The product obtained were crystallised from alcohol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 1.
UV Spectra of Hydroxydiarylsulphones.
— Ethyl Alcohol; Cyclohexane.

b) Preparation of 2- and 4-hydroxyphenyl *p*-chlorophenylsulphone

Phenyl-*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonate (13.42 g, 0.05 mole) and anhydrous aluminium chloride were taken in a round bottom flask fitted with air condenser and calcium chloride guard tube. Contents were heated slowly at 130°-140° for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture cooled and decomposed by ice and hydrochloric acid. The product was extracted with aqueous sodium hydroxide (0.5%) and precipitated by

TABLE 1. PHYSICAL DATA OF THE ARYLSULPHONATES OF TYPE R-O-SO₂-p-CHLOROPHENYL

Sr. No.	R	Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	% Sulphur	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	-Phenyl	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ SCl	89.39	90	12.00	11.87
2.	o-Cresyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ SCl	55.12	59-60	11.42	11.32
3.	m-Cresyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ SCl	54.82	46-47	11.40	11.32
4.	o-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ SCl ₂	61.44	118	11.68	10.56
5.	o-Nitrophenyl	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₅ NSCl	47.78	96-97	10.61	10.51
6.	α-Naphthyl	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₃ SCl	78.22	120-22	10.12	10.03

TABLE 2. PHYSICAL DATA OF DIARYLSULPHONES OF THE TYPE R-SO₂-p-CHLOROPHENYL

Sr. No.	R	Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	% Sulphur	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ SCl	20.81	158-9	12.00	11.87
2.	2-Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ SCl	80.12	141-42	11.44	11.32
3.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ SCl	8.13	140-41	11.97	11.87
4.	4-Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ SCl	70.42	243-44	11.40	11.32
5.	2-Hydroxy-3-methylphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ SCl	22.42	131-32	11.42	11.38
6.	2-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ SCl	78.32	250-52	10.94	10.83
7.	4-Hydroxy-2-methylphenyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ SCl	21.12	137-38	11.45	11.32
8.	4-Methoxy-2-methylphenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ SCl	72.52	243-45	11.96	10.83
9.	2-Hydroxy-3-chlorophenyl	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ SCl ₂	25.22	150	10.64	10.56
10.	2-Methoxy-3-chlorophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃ SCl ₂	77.32	169-70	10.11	10.09
11.	4-Hydroxy-3-nitrophenyl	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₅ NSCl	18.12	140-42	10.33	10.11
12.	4-Methoxy-3-nitrophenyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₅ NSCl	70.52	200-02	10.22	10.08
13.	4-Hydroxy-α-naphthyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ SCl	18.52	180-82	10.13	10.03
14.	4-Methoxy-α-naphthyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ SCl	60.38	260-62	10.80	9.62

hydrochloric acid. Yield 3.00 g (20.8%). The product was a mixture of ortho and para-isomer which was treated with hot benzene (50 ml) and filtered.

TABLE 3. ULTRAVIOLET SPECTRA OF DIARYLSULPHONES OF TYPE R-SO₂-p-CHLOROPHENYL

Sr. No.	Sr. No. of compound in Table (1)	In ethanol		In cyclohexane	
		λ max (nm)	log E	λ max (nm)	log E
1.	(1)	235	4.40	243	3.97
		275	3.87	280	3.23
		290	3.92	—	—
2.	(3)	235	4.33	250	3.92
		290	3.84	300	3.24
		—	—	—	—
3.	(5)	232	4.02	245	4.22
		242	3.95	300	3.75
		285	3.47	—	—
4.	(7)	242	4.21	230	4.53
		280	3.54	280	3.82
		295	3.75	300	3.99
5.	(9)	235	3.54	250	4.03
		280	3.65	300	3.93
		295	3.65	—	—
6.	(13)	228	4.42	220	4.14
		240	4.11	275	3.50
		285	3.88	—	—

The benzene insoluble product (0.9 g) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 141°-42°. It was identified to be ortho isomer by u.v. spectra.

The more soluble product on removal of solvent gave para-isomer (2.1 g) which was crystallised from ethanol. M.p. 158°-9°. Its constitution was supported by u.v. spectra.

Similarly, other aryl-p-chlorobenzenesulphonate was rearranged.

c) Methylation of diarylsulphones

Methylation of hydroxysulphone was carried out using dimethylsulphate⁴.

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